

INTEGRATING SPEECH COMPETENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article explores the integration of speech competence and digital technologies in teaching English as a foreign language. The focus is on the competency-based approach, which aims at the formation and development of foreign language communicative competence (FLCC), comprising linguistic, speech, and sociocultural components. Special attention is given to the development of speech competence, particularly listening and speaking skills, which are key to successful communication. An analysis of modern electronic resources shows that the use of digital tools in distance learning effectively supports the development of these skills. At the same time, objective difficulties in listening and individual learner characteristics are highlighted, which must be taken into account when designing teaching methodologies. In conclusion, it is stated that a well-designed methodology incorporating digital technologies can significantly enhance students' speech training and strengthen their overall foreign language communicative competence.

Keywords: foreign language communicative competence, speech competence, listening, speaking, distance learning, digital technologies, electronic resources, teaching methodology, foreign language, skills development.

It is well known that the competency-based approach in education is aimed at the formation and development of a comprehensive set of competencies in students, the acquisition of which enables them to effectively solve various professional tasks. The main goal of foreign language instruction is the development of foreign language

communicative competence (FLCC). Numerous studies in Russian academic literature (authors: N.I. Almazova, I.L. Bim, M.N. Vyatyutnev, N.I. Gez, N.D. Galskova, I.A. Zimnyaya, G.A. Kitaigorodskaya, E.I. Passov, V.V. Safonova, E.N. Solovova, A.N. Shamov, and others) are dedicated to the content and methodology of foreign language teaching within the framework of the competency-based approach. According to T.P. Popova, the concept of FLCC "undergoes reinterpretation in response to changes in social reality and the evolving goals of foreign language education in society." [1, c. 11]. Following V.V. Safonova, we understand foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) as the degree to which a learner has acquired linguistic, speech, and sociocultural knowledge, skills, and abilities, enabling them to flexibly and appropriately adjust their speech behavior in accordance with the psychological characteristics of a given communicative situation. [2]. In general, scholars identify various components that make up foreign language communicative competence (FLCC). According to the model proposed by V.V. Safonova, FLCC consists of linguistic, speech, and sociocultural components. The sociocultural component, in turn, is divided into sociolinguistic, subject-specific, general cultural, and country-specific (linguocultural) competences.[3]. Linguistic competence involves mastering the phonetic, orthographic, grammatical, and lexical means of the language. Its development must occur in close connection with both speech and sociocultural competences. Speech competence implies the development of communicative skills across all four main types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, and writing. This study focuses on improving speech competence in English language lessons. The aim of the article is to analyze a range of electronic resources that facilitate the development of listening and speaking skills in the context of distance learning.

Regarding difficulties in teaching listening, according to E.N. Solovova, listening is the skill that causes the greatest number of problems both for beginners learning a foreign language and for those preparing for international exams to assess language proficiency. [4]. Among the main difficulties of listening, the researcher primarily highlights that the text is played only once, and the listener does not have the opportunity to adjust the speaker's speech to their own level of understanding. In real-life situations, repetitions are impossible, and the speech may be fast, emotional, and filled with figurative expressions that are not always easy to recognize in the flow of speech. Since a lot of listening is required in live communication, the ability to accurately and fully perceive the interlocutor's speech is of great importance for successful communication. Therefore, one of the key objectives of foreign language teaching is to develop students' ability to understand spoken language. At the same time, listening, like any other type of speech activity in foreign language lessons, serves not only as a goal but also as a means of learning, since it is impossible to develop only one skill in isolation. By working with audio texts, students simultaneously improve their phonetic, lexical, and grammatical skills. Moreover, audio materials always contain information that forms the basis for the further development of speaking and writing skills. Besides difficulties related to the one-time listening and individual characteristics of the speaker, there are also challenges caused by the listening conditions and linguistic features of the material. These include the use of a large number of unfamiliar words, idiomatic expressions, colloquial phrases, and

ellipses — that is, phrases in which some parts of the sentence are omitted but are common for native speakers and understandable to dialogue participants within context. [5 c. 127].

Thus, the development of foreign language communicative competence, as a key objective of foreign language education, is impossible without the comprehensive formation of all its components — linguistic, speech, and sociocultural. Special attention should be paid to speech competence, as it ensures the practical use of the language in real communicative situations. One of the most important components of speech activity is listening, which, despite its complexity, plays a crucial role in forming effective communication. An analysis of modern electronic resources has shown that the use of digital tools in the context of distance learning can effectively contribute to the development of listening and speaking skills. However, it is necessary to take into account both the objective difficulties of listening and the individual characteristics of learners. Therefore, a well-structured methodology that incorporates digital technologies can significantly enhance students' speech training and, as a result, strengthen their overall foreign language communicative competence.

REFERENCES:

1. Lipko, Y.G., & Antipyeva, I.A. (2022). Improving speech competence in English language lessons within the framework of distance learning. *Irkutsk*, 32(2), 432–439.
2. Bim I.L. Competence Approach to Education and Teaching Foreign Languages. In Khutorskoy A.V. (ed.). *Competences in Education: Design Experience*. Moscow, 2007, pp. 156–163. (In Russian).
3. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. *Theory of Teaching Foreign Languages: Linguodidactics and Methodology*. Moscow, Akademiya Publ., 2013. 336 p.
4. Zimnyaya I.A. Key Competencies as Effectively Target Basis of Competency Approach in Education. Moscow, Research Center for Problems of Quality in Specialists' Training Publ., 2004. 48 p. 439 Известия Байкальского государственного университета. 2022. Т. 32, № 2. С. 432–439 ISSN 2500-2759
5. Popova T.P. *Formation of Foreign Language Communicative Competence among Students of the Correspondence Department of a Language University*. Lobachevsky State University of Nizhny Novgorod Publ., 2013. 186 p.
6. Safonova V.V. *The Study of Languages of International Communication in the Context of Dialogue of Cultures and Civilizations*. Voronezh, Istoki Publ., 1996. 238 p.
7. Safonova V.V. *Sociocultural Approach to Teaching a Foreign Language as a Specialty*. Doct. Diss. Thesis. Moscow, 1992. 50 p. 7. Solovova E.N. *Training Methodology of Foreign Languages*. 3rd ed. Moscow, Prosveshchenie Publ., 2005. 239 p.
8. Pavlyukevich L.V., Osokina T.A. Peculiarities of Using TubeQuizard as a Teaching Tool at a Foreign Language Lesson. *Problemy romano-germanskoj filologii, pedagogiki i metodiki prepodavaniya inostrannykh yazykov = Problems of Romano-Germanic Philology, Pedagogy and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages*, 2019, no. 15, pp. 145–149. (In Russian).

9. Kiseleva Yu.V. About the Problem of Critical Thinking Formation of Students in Higher Educational Establishment. *Credo New*, 2012, no. 1. Available at: http://www.intelros.ru/readroom/credo_new/credo-new-2012-1/13145-k-probleme-formirovaniya-kriticheskogo-myshleniya-studenta-vuza.html. (In Russian).
10. Bagrova A.Ya. The Method of Projects in Training in Foreign Languages. *Vestnik Moskovskogo instituta lingvistiki = Vestnik of the Moscow Institute of Linguistics*, 2015, no. 1, pp. 12–17. (In Russian).
11. Amanullaeva Kamola Muminovna. National concepts and their literary representation in Haruki Murakami’s novel “IQ84” *Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe (East European Scientific Journal) № 9(25)*, 2017. <https://sciencescholar.us/journal/index.php/ijhs/article/view/11004>
12. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. Художественный концепт и специфические характеристики его воссоздания, *Хорижий филология №4*, Самарқанд. СамДЧТИ. 2020, Б.53-57. https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/foreign_philology/article/view/1579
13. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna, Universal concept as structural formation of the component of Haruki Murakami’s novel “Kafka on the Shore” *Jour of Adv research in Dynamical & Control Systems*, Vol. 12, Issue- 2020, Scopus, Б.1117-1121. <https://sciencescholar.us/journal/index.php/ijhs/article/view/11004>
14. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. О художественном концепте и в целом, *Россия и Узбекистан Международные образовательные научные и социально-культурные технологии: векторы развития. Челябинск-Ташкент-Бухара-Самарканд 2020*. Б.271-272.
15. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. The role of translation in science. *Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History*. 2023, 60-62 p.
16. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. The concept of translation and characteristics of fetures. *Information Horizons: American Journal of Library and Information Science*. 2024, 63-66 p.
17. Nasrullayeva Tozagul Suxrobovna, Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. Peculiarities of translation of Technical Terms, Concepts and Rendering articles in technical translation. *American journal of social and humanitarian research*, 2023. – С.29-33.
18. Kubayeva Nafisa, Amanullayeva Kamola. The problem of teaching students lexical and phraseological features in translation studies of phrasal verbs in English and Uzbek languages. *Eurasian journal of academic research*. 39-42 p. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/37844>

19. О.А.Алижонова, К.М.Амануллаева, М.Б.Аскарова. Использование термина концепт в лингвокультурологии. Вестник магистратуры. 2024.№12-2 (159) С.76-78
20. К.Амануллаева, О.Алижонова. Роль лингвокультурологии в лингвистике. Ijtimoiy-gumanitar va tabiiy fanlardagi an'anaviy va zamonaviy yondashuvlar dialektikasi. Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman. 27-Fevral, 2025. С.324-325.